

Dyes derived from β -Phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic Acid.

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In a previous paper by one of the present authors (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 123, 225) it was shown that diphenic anhydride condenses with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds to form dyestuffs analogous to the phthaleins. In a previous paper by Ghosh (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, 115, 1102) it was shown that quinolinic anhydride condenses with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds to form similar dyestuffs. From observations on these substances he concluded that the effect of nitrogen in the ring was to lighten the colour. But he did not measure the intensities of colour in the two series. Quantitative experiments on absorption spectra, which are now in progress in this laboratory, tend to show that the effect of the nitrogen atom in the ring is to intensify the colour instead of diminishing it. In order to obtain conclusive results further dyes have been prepared by condensing β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid with aromatic amino and hydroxy compounds, which are analogous in constitution to the diphenicins with the exception that they contain a nitrogen atom in the ring. These compounds are much more intense in colour than the corresponding diphenicins. The details of these quantitative experiments will be communicated later.

Resorcinol- β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

A mixture of β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid (1 mol.) and resorcinol (2 mols) was heated with a few drops of sulphuric acid at 180-200° for about an hour. The melt was extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic extract after filtration was diluted with water which caused the precipitation of the colouring matter in flocks. It was purified by precipitation from alkaline solution by dilute acid. It was thus obtained as a yellowish brown powder which sinters at 186° and melts with decomposition at 200°. The solution in alkali has an orange red colour and a light green fluorescence. (Found : C=73·28; H=4·2. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C=73·34 ; H=3·7 per cent).

Catechol- β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

A mixture of β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid (1 mol.), catechol (2 mols.) and stannic chloride (1 mol. plus 20 per cent. excess) was heated at 100-110° for about three hours. The melt was then poured into water and after through grinding the insoluble residue was washed with water. It was then extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic extract was diluted with water which caused the precipitation of the dyestuff as a crystalline powder. It is a colourless substance. The solution in alkali has a transient green colour. It does not melt at 310°. (Found : C=73·6 ; H=4·5. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C=73·34 ; H=3·7 per cent.).

Phloroglucinol-β-phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

The condensation was effected as in the case of resorcinol with the difference that the temperature was kept at 150-170°. The product was isolated in a similar manner. It is a bright yellow crystalline powder which does not melt at 280°. The solution in alkali has an orange-red colour. (Found : C=67·2 ; H=3·2. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_7\text{N}$ requires C=67·5 ; H=3·3 per cent.).

Hydroxyquinol-β-phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

The condensation was effected as in the case of resorcinol and the substance was isolated in a similar manner. It is a light brown powder which melts with decomposition at 228-230°. The solution in alkali has a fine pink colour. (Found : C=68·5 ; H=4·09. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_7\text{N}$ requires C=67·5 ; H=3·3 per cent.).

m-Diethyl-amidophenol-β-phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

A mixture of β-phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid (1 mol.) and *m*-diethyl-amidophenol (2 mol.) was heated with a few drops of strong sulphuric acid at 160-170° for about two hours. The melt was then extracted with alcohol and the alcoholic extract, after filtration, was diluted with water which caused the precipitation of the

colouring matter in purple flocks. This was filtered and purified by dissolving in dilute hydrochloric acid and precipitating with dilute sodium carbonate. It is a reddish violet crystalline powder which dissolves in dilute acids and also in organic solvents the solution has a brilliant pink colour and a brown fluorescence. It melts at 193°. (Found : N = 9.07. $C_{28}H_{23}O_3N_3$ requires N = 9.1 per cent.).

m-Phenylene-diamine- β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylein.

A mixture of β -phenyl-pyridine-dicarboxylic acid (1 mol.) and *m*-phenylene-diamine hydrochloride (2 mols. plus 10 per cent. excess) was heated at 180-190° for about three hours. The melt was allowed to cool and after grinding to a fine powder was extracted with absolute alcohol. The alcoholic extract after boiling with animal charcoal was concentrated to a small volume and the dyestuff crystallised as light brown needles. It melts with decomposition at 154° and dissolves in organic solvents and dilute acids. The solution has an orange colour and a green fluorescence. (Found : N = 13.5. $C_{25}H_{19}O_2N_4$ requires N = 13.7 per cent.).

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